

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT PROCESS OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH DELAMINATION

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SUMMARY: Several important issues regarding impact and damage simulation of composite plates due to low velocity were investigated including contact law, damage initiation and the corresponding change of stiffness, and damping. Computer simulation was carried out to demonstrate the low-velocity impact process of composite plates with delamination in this paper. Continuum damaged mechanics was applied to account for the change of mechanical properties of damaged materials. The Hertzian contact law was modified in order to accommodate the serious damage in the plate. A semi-empirical delamination damage criterion was introduced. A finite element program written in FORTRAN was developed to analyze the transient dynamic response of composite plates with delamination. Results including the force history and delamination areas were found to correlate well with the experiments.

KEYWORDS: composite laminate with delamination, low-velocity impact, impact simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite materials have been known very sensitive to impact damage. For example, barely visible impact damage can contribute up to 60% loss in an aircraft composite structure's compressive strength. Compared with traditional metal materials, composite materials are relatively new and complex, even though many publications on impact damage of composites can be found in the literature, many of their characteristics still remain mysterious, especially the theories regarding impact tolerance and after-impact residual properties. The contact law proposed by Yang and Sun [1] has successfully coupled the equations of motions of impactor and composites. It has also simplified the computation of the damage simulation. However, the effect of serious impact damage was not taken into account. On the other hand, the change of material module due to damage is another challenging issue because no data can be retrieved directly from impact experiments. Belingardi et al. [2] and Luo et al. [3] adopted the simple assumption that when damage occurs during impact, the mechanical properties of the damaged materials would reduce to certain levels regardless of the extent of damage. However, based on experimental results, impact damage would continue to develop after the initial damage appears. A model is needed to simulate the gradual change of material properties. The impact induced delamination is the most important damage mode because the level of impact energy to initiate delamination is low and the post-impact compressive strength is dramatically reduced due to delamination. Because of the complex nature of laminated composites, a simple and effective criterion for the delamination initiation is still lacking.

The stability of simulation computation is another issue to be considered. This is especially true when the tremendous changes of material properties due to the damage in composites are taken into account. The instability or divergence of the computation might be caused by the specific algorithms in some cases. However, in most cases, they are the results of inappropriate physical modes. Increasing the damping coefficient at damage areas is an effective way to stabilize the computation and this can be explained based on impact results.

By addressing each of the concerns, a finite element program written in FORTRAN using 20-noded solid hexahedral elements with layered structure was developed. The Wilson- θ scheme was adopted to perform time integration for the motion equations for the impactor and composites plate system. The computer simulation of low-velocity impact process of composite plates with delamination is performed and the results correlated with experiments well.

CONTACT LAW

Contact law plays a very important role in impact analyses by coupling the motion of the impactor and the target and it greatly simplifies the damage simulation. Based on experiment results, impact damage can be regarded as local damage and global damage. The local damage is located directly under the impactor and is essentially associated with the geometry and material properties of the impactor. On the other hand, the global damage is generally referred to the damage initiated from the impact point and is mainly in the form of delamination. Even though the local damage has relatively small effects on the post-impact mechanical properties of composite laminates, it is one of the essential parameters when formulating the impact simulation.

Yang and Sun [1] modified the Hertzian contact law through a systematic experimental study. The modified contact law can be applied to determine the relation between the contact force and indentation during both loading and unloading:

$$\text{Loading} \quad f = k\alpha^{1.5} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Unloading} \quad f = f_{\max} \left(\frac{\alpha - \alpha_0}{\alpha_{\max} - \alpha_0} \right)^{2.5} \quad (2)$$

Where k is contact stiffness. α and α_0 are indentation and permanent indentation. respectively f_{\max} is the maximum contact force, and α_{\max} is its corresponding indentation. k and α_0 are material dependent and can be determined by experiments [1]. Even though these equations do not account for the change of stiffness due to impact damage, they have been widely used in the impact simulation studies. Lagace et al. [4] addressed the effect of damage on the indentation and impact behavior in their experimental investigation. Based on their observation, they have concluded that the contact stiffness of damaged laminates is larger than the undamaged laminates and that there are no detectable effects on the global structural response due to impact damage. On the contrary, Shahid and Chang [5] assumed that impact damage affects the contact behavior. They modified the contact stiffness of Hertzian law using the weighted average stiffness of the plies, including undamaged and damaged, through the laminate thickness so that the contact stiffness decreases as the impact damage develops.

Experimental results from low velocity impact of composite plates show that there is a distinct dent left on the impacted surface after an impact of a certain energy level. As the

impact energy increases, the permanent dent becomes deeper until the plate is perforated. In computer simulation, the impact usually begins when the impactor comes into contact with the plate and ends when the impactor rebounds and loses contact with the plate. The criterion most researchers use to define the end of impact is that the impactor rebounds to the location which is α_0 under the location of initial contact. However, the location where the impactor loses contact with the plate is d_0 , depth of permanent dent, under the location of initial contact and α_0 is the permanent indentation, which is the permanent change of plate thickness. This commonly used criterion is actually using Equation (2) and setting the depth of permanent dent d_0 equal to the permanent indentation α_0 because the deformation of the backside of the plate is not taken into account. This is considered appropriate if the impact energy is at the moderate level when the back surface of the plate is not protruded. However, if the impact energy is so high that d_0 is no longer equal to α_0 due to the protrusion on the back side of the plate; this approach will result in a major error in modeling the impact process. Furthermore, when serious damages occurred, the permanent indentation is beyond the range considered by the existing empirical function which correlates the maximum impact force and permanent indentation. Therefore, the following equation describing the contact force during unloading as a function of the impact force at the beginning of rebound f_m , impactor displacement u and impactor displacement at the beginning of rebound u_m , and depth of permanent dent d_0 is proposed:

$$\text{Modified unloading}^{[6]} \quad f = f_m \left(\frac{u - d_0}{u_m - d_0} \right)^n \quad (3)$$

In Equation (3), n is used to adjust the nonlinear relation of the contact force and the displacement caused by the damage of the plate. The depth of permanent dent d_0 can be obtained from experiments or can be estimated, after further studies, from other impact damage state parameters.

The laminate responds to the impactor in two modes: vibratory mode and the major loading and unloading mode. The former is caused by the dynamic response of the impacted plate and the latter is based on the contact law as well as the flexural displacement of the plate. As discussed previously, Equation (1) with constant contact stiffness was adopted for the loading portion of both modes of response. Equation (2) is used for the unloading of the vibratory mode. Equation (3) is used to govern unloading contact law only in the major unloading mode.

IMPACT INDUCED DELAMINATION CRITERION

The impact damage model adopted assumes that the intraply matrix cracking is the initial damage mode. The delamination and fiber breakage might occur subsequently. The semi-empirical delamination criterion [6] is based on the previous research results:

$$\left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{33,n}}{Z_c} \right)^2 + D_s \sin \theta_n \frac{(\bar{\sigma}_{23,n})^2 + (\bar{\sigma}_{13,n+1})^2}{S^2} + D_t \sin \theta_n \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{22,n+1}}{Y} \right)^2 = e_D \quad (4)$$

Where D_s and D_t are material constants, $\bar{\sigma}$ represents the average stress in each ply, the subscripts 1,2,3 denote the fiber, in-plane transverse, and out-of-plane directions, respectively,

of each ply. The subscripts n and $n+1$ correspond to the upper and lower plies of the n th interface. Z_c is out-of-plane compression strength, and S is in-plane shear strength. Y is the transverse tensile or compressive strength. θ_n is the difference of fiber angles between the two plies adjacent to the n th interface. The e_D in Equation (4) is regarded as the failure index. When $e_D \geq 1$ delamination occurs in the n th interface and when $e_D < 1$ no delamination occurs. The equation contains all the important stresses that cause delamination. D_s and D_t can be estimated from experiments and trial calculations.

DAMPING AND COMPUTATION STABILITY

The dynamic response of the impactor can be ignored during the simulation because the impactor is generally made of steel with high density and mass [6]. However, the dynamic response of the laminate can be remarkable. The dynamic response of the laminate is shown as the oscillation of both the impact force and the flexural displacement of the laminate. When the stiffness of the laminate is reduced due to impact damage according to the present damage model, the amplitude of the laminate vibration will be enlarged at the damaged areas. This change in laminate displacement enlarges the difference between the laminate displacement and the impactor displacement, leading to severe oscillation in impact force according to the contact law. The abrupt change in impact force in turn enhances the dynamic response of the laminate causing very complicated interactions. In most cases, a computational error due to divergence will occur. In order to eliminate the computational instability, material damping is considered. Usually, material damping is ignored in low velocity impact analysis because it has little effects on the impact process if damage is not considered. However, when impact damage is present, the properties of damaged material will change and the material damping will increase dramatically. The material damping has important effects on the dynamic behavior of the plate at the damaged locations. Energy dissipation due to damping can actually stabilize computation. In the present study, only material damping is taken into account. This will dissipate the kinetic energy of the plate and, more importantly, stabilize the simulation computation when serious impact damage occurs. For the j th ply in the i th element, the material damping coefficient $\beta^{i,j}$ can be chosen as:

$$\beta^{i,j} = \beta_0 + r[t_{11}(D_f) + t_{22}(D_m) + t_{33}(D_d)] \quad (5)$$

Where β_0 is material damping coefficient for undamaged laminate and r is a constant to be determined from trial calculations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

T300/QY8911 (graphite/epoxy) composite plates, with material properties listed in Tables 1 and 2, are selected. The specimens are [45/-45/0/-45/0/45/90/45/0/-45/90/-45/0/45/90/0]_s, 100mm×75mm×3.8mm composites with a centric 38mm-diameter circular delamination located between the 8th and 9th plies. The impactor mass is 5kg with a hemispherical tip of 12.5mm in diameter.

Table 1: Material properties of T300/QY8911

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12}	ν_{12}	(kg/m^3)
130	9.75	4.5	0.33	1.614

Table 2: Strength characteristics of T300/QY8911

X_t (MPa)	X_c (MPa)	Y_t (MPa)	Y_c (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)
1561	1226	80	218	89.9

An impact of 24J in energy was simulated as an example to demonstrate the impact and damage process. The results are given in Figures 1-3. Figure 1 shows the simulated force history using models with and without delamination during the impact duration. It can be seen that the results based on the model are consistent with the experimental force history shown in Figure 4. Figure 2 shows the time history of the impactor velocity and Figure 3 shows the change of kinetic energy of the impactor as function of time.

Fig. 1: Impact force history

As shown in the Figure 1, Figure 4 and Figure 5, the impact and damage processes can be observed as five stages which are separated by P1, P2, P3, and P4.

Stage 1 – From the beginning of impact to P1: The impact force increases rapidly but relatively smooth. The regular undulations of the impact force are caused by the vibration effects of the impacted plate. At P1, slight damage in the forms of matrix cracking and delamination has initiated. Therefore, P1 can be regarded as the initiation of impact damage.

Stage 2 – P1 to P2: In this stage, the impact force reaches its maximum at P2 with intensive random fluctuation caused by rapid development of impact damage. The rate of increase of impact force is a little lower than the first stage. The impact damage developed quickly in this stage.

Stage 3 – P2 to P3: The impact force drops from its maximum to a comparatively steady value while its fluctuation remains very intensive. Damage expands mainly near the middle of the plate and at P3 the damage area almost reaches its peak.

Fig. 2: Velocity of impactor

Fig.3: Variation of kinetic energy of impactor.

Fig.4: Experimental impact force history

Stage 4 – P3 to P4: The impact force becomes steady compared with the two previous stages. The amplitude of force fluctuation decreases but the impactor is still pressing into the plate until P4, where the velocity of impactor becomes zero. In this stage, the damage develops mainly in degrees. The delamination area reaches its maximum at the end of this stage.

Stage 5 – P4 to the end of the impact: This is the last stage of impact process. The impact force begins to decrease and the amplitude of the random fluctuation becomes small. The motion of the impacted plate and impactor are all in their rebounding state. No further damage development is accessed in the stage. At the end of the impact, the impactor leaves the plate at a rather low velocity compared with the initial impact velocity (Figure 2). The cost kinetic energy of the impactor is absorbed by the damage of the plate.

Fig.5: Impact force history of composite plates with delamination

Fig.6: Delamination Area

Figure 6 shows the dalaminaton area. It should be noted that the 16th interface showed no delamination and this is because it is the interface between plies of same fiber direction.

Compared with impact of composite plates without delamination (Figure 1 and Figure 4), the peak value of impact force is lower and the impact duration becomes longer. And the delamination area is greater (Figure 6).

CONCLUSION

A computational model has been developed in this investigation to simulate the process and damage of low-velocity impact of composite laminates with delamination. The contact law greatly simplified the impact and damage analysis, precluding the complicated contact and damage analysis around the impact point. A delamination criterion [6] is proposed to be used in impact simulation. The continuum damage mechanics analysis is introduced into impact damage with assumed compliance variation functions. The damping effects of damaged material are considered in the simulation to increase the calculation stability and to improve the accuracy of the simulation. The developed model is comparable with impact test data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by FanZhou Fund under Grant No.20030501 and NSFC under Grant No.10477003.

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